

SECANT NEWSLETTER

Security and privacy protection in Internet of Things

Issue #5

April 2024

Welcome to the 5th SECANT Newsletter!

We are pleased to announce the publication of the fifth issue of the SECANT newsletter.

SECANT is a 3-year Research and Innovation Action from 2021 to 2024 funded under Horizon 2020.

It kicked off in September 2021 and it gathers a consortium of 19 partners from 10 different countries including large ICT industries, SMEs, research institutes, 1 healthcare organization and 1 EU CERT.

With just 5 months remaining until the conclusion of the SECANT project, the Consortium remains focused on the objectives of the project and the final touches on the tools' functionalities, the Use Cases and the platform's integration.

Several milestones were achieved over the recent period, notably the SECANT second round of integration and the finalization of crucial components. These milestones are described in detail in this newsletter edition.

Table of Contents

p.2	p.3	p.4	p.5
Milestones	6 th Plenary Meeting	SECANT events	Synergies

PROJECT INFORMATION

SECANT: SECurity And privacy protection in IoT devices

Grant Agreement ID: 101019645

Start Date: 1 September 2021
End Date: 31 August 2024

Funded under: H2020-EU.3.7.4,
H2020-EU.3.7.

Overall budget: 6.567.958,75
EU contribution: 5.202.226,38

Coordinated by: NTT DATA SPAIN

STAY TUNED!

Stay updated on all our latest news, developments, research and general information regarding the SECANT project.

www.secant-project.eu

[@SecantProject](https://twitter.com/SecantProject)

[secant-project](https://www.linkedin.com/company/secant-project)

[secant](https://zenodo.org/communities/secant)

Milestones

It is with great pleasure to share the latest developments of the SECANT project. Over the recent period, our collaborative efforts have led to significant milestones across various project activities, highlighting our **commitment to innovation**.

Cyber Security Risk Assessment in Connected ICT Ecosystems

Firstly, regarding the "Cyber Security Risk Assessment in Connected ICT Ecosystems", we have achieved the **final versions of crucial components**, including the Technical Vulnerability and Impact Assessment Module, Taxonomy for Healthcare-related Attacks, and Techniques for Dynamic Taxonomies Generation, have been completed. These milestones underscore our dedication to addressing **cybersecurity challenges in connected environments**.

Trusted and Secure Data Sharing

Furthermore, concerning the "Trusted and Secure Data Sharing", we have successfully completed the implementation and compliance assessment of the **Trusted Application Module (TAM)**, further reinforcing the security and integrity of data sharing processes.

2nd Round of Integration

We are thrilled to announce the release of the second round of integration for the SECANT prototype. This achievement represents a significant step forward in enhancing the functionality and performance of our platform, bringing us closer to our ultimate goals: the development of the **SECANT Final Integrated Platform**. This achievement marks a pivotal moment in our project's evolution, showcasing the seamless integration of diverse components into a **unified solution**.

SECANT Use Cases

Lastly, for the Use-Cases, we have finalised the "Pilot Evaluation Framework and Measures Specifications." This will serve as a vital tool in assessing the **effectiveness and impact of our solutions in real-world scenarios**. The 4 Use Cases will be implemented in the coming months and presented to the end users to gather valuable feedback. Their feedback will be carefully considered to ensure delivering better added value and benefit for the end users.

Additionally, our partners are actively engaged in driving innovation outputs, further expanding the scope and impact of our project.

USE CASE #1

Protecting the connected ambulance of the future

[Read More](#)

USE CASE #2

Cyber security for connected medical devices and mobile applications

[Read More](#)

USE CASE #3

Health data protection in the healthcare supply chain

[Read More](#)

USE CASE #4

Cyber Security Training

[Read More](#)

Highlight: SECANT 6th Plenary Meeting

On 14-15 March 2024, SECANT successfully organized its 6th Plenary Meeting in Thessaloniki, Greece and specifically at the premises of our partner, Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH). With just 5 months remaining in the SECANT project, the agenda of this two-day meeting focused heavily on preparing and executing the project's technical aspects.

During the first day, the SECANT consortium delved into **technical discussions** focusing mainly on reviewing:

- The Final Architecture and workflows
- The Tool Functionalities
- The SECANT Integration
- The 4 Use Cases

Additionally, a Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Workshop was conducted, emphasizing the **innovation outputs** of SECANT and the dissemination approach ahead. Finally, the Project Management Team discussed important coordination aspects.

During the second day, the meeting's agenda included a long workshop on the SECANT **Use Cases** and the respective pilots, along with a dedicated session for the **Final Review preparation**.

The SECANT consortium discussed the project's final Plenary Meeting, which will be announced soon.

SECANT events

SECANT chaired and participated at the joint "**Cyber Threat Intelligence: Empowering IoT Security**" workshop. The workshop was an initiative of the SecureCyber Cluster – Enhancing Cybersecurity and focused on the efforts of 9 EU-funded projects that have developed a Cyber Threat Intelligence component, specifically emphasizing IoT systems into several vertical industries.

Mar
06

Mar
14-15

On 14-15 March 2024, we successfully conducted our **6th Plenary Meeting** in Thessaloniki, Greece. The meeting was hosted by our partner, CERTH, and was attended by the entire SECANT consortium.

Our partner, DNSC, represented SECANT at its booth at the **BSides Transylvania** in Cluj-Napoca, Romania, giving the opportunity to all attendees to learn more about our project and its envisioned outcomes. The event gathered more than 800 participants, with SECANT being introduced to over 400 individuals covering the public and private sectors, academia and students.

Mar
23

Mar
28

Our colleague, Octavian Popa, from DNSC participated at the **Digital Innovation Zone Conference** which was held in Iasi, Romania. Specifically, he participated at the panel discussion "Technological trends and practical solutions for development through digitalization" and highlighted the significance of digitizing the healthcare sector, emphasizing the objectives of SECANT.

2nd Coffee Meeting with **EXTERNAL ADVISORY BOARD**

On the 1st of March 2024, the SECANT consortium presented the latest updates of the project to the project's External Advisory Board, gaining valuable feedback towards the finalization of the project's solutions.

Synergies

Joint Cyber Threat Intelligence: Empowering IoT Security Workshop

[Link](#) for video

SECANT project chaired and presented during the joint workshop "Cyber Threat Intelligence: Empowering IoT Security", organized by the "SecureCyber Cluster –enhancing cybersecurity" on May 1st 2024. Over 70 participants joined this online workshop, which featured presentations and live demos from 9 EU funded H2020 projects, namely: CROSSCON, ERATOSTHENES, IRIS, SENTINEL, SPATIAL, ARCADIAN-IoT, IDUNN and ELECTRON.

Its objective was to present the efforts of multiple EU-funded projects that have developed a Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) component, with a specific emphasis on IoT systems. SECANT showcased how the project uses AI-based CTI in the healthcare ecosystem. SECANT was well-represented by three partners: NTTDATA, CERTH and 8BELLS.

SECANT'S new collaboration with ENTRUST

The SECANT project is pleased to announce a new collaboration as part of its networking and clustering activities with the ENTRUST project (GA No 101095634). ENTRUST sits at the forefront of digital transformation for the Healthcare domain as it moves into the next generation of Connected Medical Devices (CMD), where the expansion of connectivity and data processing capabilities and resources at the edge have revolutionized the health sector by improving outcomes, lowering healthcare costs, and enhancing patient safety. The ENTRUST innovations not only disrupt the CMD value chain and impact all stakeholders by putting dynamic trust assessment as a new dimension of quality of a 'devices' operational profile but are also a significant driver to overcome existing gaps in the security of such complex systems.

Annoucement: Joining forces with the SecureCyber Cluster – Enhancing Cybersecurity

SECANT project joins forces with other EU-funded projects to inaugurate the "SecureCyber Cluster – Enhancing Cybersecurity". This pioneering collaboration, officially launched online, unites various cybersecurity projects under a singular umbrella to bolster collective efforts against evolving threats.

Already engaged in joint seminars, workshops, webinars and the Horizon Results Booster programme, the cluster endeavours to spread awareness and propagate best practices in cybersecurity. The horizon anticipates further synergies throughout 2024, such as the Joint Cyber Threat Intelligence: Empowering IoT Security Workshop, mentioned above.

The SECANT project, among other EU H2020 projects such as IDUNN, KRAKEN, ELECTRON, CROSSCON, TRUSTaWARE, IRIS, SPATIAL, ERATOSTHENES, SENTINEL, and ARCADIAN-IoT, brings its unique perspective to fortify the cluster's initiatives.

Click [here](#) to follow the LinkedIn page and stay updated about the upcoming joint activities!

The SECANT consortium

3 Large ICT industries

NTT DATA

THALES
Building a future we can all trust

SIMAVI
Software Imagination & Vision

9 SMEs

EIGHTBELLS
Independent Research & Consultancy

UBITECH
ubiquitous solutions

axon logic

**INFO
LYSIS**

**ianus
consulting**

EXALENS®

**Security Labs
Consulting**

adrestia
Enabling a Network & Cloud world

bi²S Ltd
Business and IoT
Integrated Solutions

5 research institutes and universities

Karolinska Institutet

i2cat

iti Information
Technologies
Institute

**TIC
Salut Social**

**UNIVERSITY OF
SURREY**

1 healthcare organization

**POLARIS
Medical**

1 European CERT

**CENTRUL NATIONAL DE RĂSPUNS LA INCIDENTE
DE SECURITATE CIBERNETICĂ - CERT-RO**

twitter

@SecantProject

Visit our website:
www.secant-project.eu

Download SECANT material:

zenodo secant-project

linkedin

secant-project

[Click here to subscribe to the SECANT newsletter.](#)